

Join of 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) frags. 26 and 48

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The edition of 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) consists of fragments preserving parts of Genesis 22 through Exodus 8 as well as twenty-three tiny unidentified fragments (4Q1 frags. 38-61) which had previously been assigned to or associated with 4Q1 on the basis of physical and palaeographic features. In earlier posts on Zenodo I called attention to more 4Q1 fragments that were not included in the edition, and I proposed joins of several of the published unidentified 4Q1 fragments.

This note joins the unidentified fragment 4Q1 frag. 48 to the conglomerate of fragments now numbered 4Q1 frag. 26 in lines 9-11 of 4Q1 frags. 22 ii, 26 (Exodus 5:8-11). The resulting join can be transcribed as follows (with the writing of frag. 48 indicated in red):

גלכה ונזבחה לאלהינו תכבד ה[עבדה על האנשים ויעשו בה ואל]	9
ישעו בדברי שקר ויצאו ^ג [גשי] העם ושט[ריו ויאמרו אל העם לאמר]	10
[כה א]מר פרעה אינני [נ]תן לכם תבן אתם [לכו קחו לכם תבן]	11

The skin of the different pieces of this conglomerate fragment is somewhat distorted, making it difficult to restore the exact spatial relationship between the fragments. Remarkably on fragment 48 is the intralinear letter, possibly a *nun*. This could be the *nun* of נגשי if that word was a supralinear correction of another word.

4Q1 frag. 26 + frag. 48 joined with Gimp; images taken from <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284246>
PAM 43.006 (photo Najib Anton Albina)

Bibliography

Edition:

James R. Davila, "1. 4QGen-Exod^a," in *Qumran Cave 4 VII: Genesis to Numbers*, ed. Eugene Ulrich and Frank Moore Cross; Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XII (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1994)

Identification of 4Q1 fragments:

Eibert Tigchelaar, "Three Additional 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) Fragments." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4302465> (2020)

———, "PAM 43.689 frag. 33 (IAA Plate 90 frags. 86-88) Identified as a 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) fragment (Gen 32:29-30?)." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5503557> (2021)

———, "4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) Frag. 60 + 4Q49 (4QJudg^a)." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5114482> (2021)

———, "Join of 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) frags. 9 and 47." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5525212> (2021)

———, "Join of 4Q1 (4QGen-Exod^a) frags. 5 and 46." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5528230> (2021)